

Seroprevalence of *Taenia solium* Cysticercosis from Pigs in Zuru Local Government Area, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Taenia solium taeniosis/cysticercosis complex is a significant global public health and economic burden, contributing to neurocysticercosis in humans and financial losses in the pig farming industry due to pork downgrading. The disease remains endemic in many developing regions, including Nigeria, where poor sanitation and inadequate meat inspection facilitate its transmission. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of *T. solium* cysticercosis in pigs from the Zuru area of Kebbi State, Nigeria. A total of 184 pig sera samples were analyzed using antigen-ELISA to detect *T. solium* secretory/excretory antigens. The association between infection status and host factors (sex and age) was evaluated statistically. Of the 184 pig sera tested, 60 (32.6%) were positive for *T. solium* antigens, indicating active cysticercosis. There was no statistically significant association between sex and seroprevalence ($p = 0.416$); however, a significant association was observed between age and infection ($p = 0.002$), with older pigs exhibiting higher prevalence rates. The high seroprevalence of *T. solium* cysticercosis in pigs from the study area suggests an ongoing transmission cycle, posing a serious risk to public health and the local pig farming industry. Inadequate meat inspection and poor sanitation may contribute to the continued spread of the parasite, increasing the likelihood of human taeniosis and neurocysticercosis. Urgent interventions, including strengthened meat inspection, improved public health education, and targeted control measures, are necessary to mitigate the zoonotic and economic risks associated with *T. solium* transmission.

Keywords: Cysticercosis, Pigs, Prevalence, Slaughter, Soil.

1.0 Introduction

Cysticercosis and taeniosis are significant yet neglected parasitic zoonotic infections caused by different stages in the life cycle of the same parasite, *Taenia solium*, commonly known as the pork tapeworm [1]. Pigs serve as the typical intermediate hosts, while humans are the only definitive hosts, harboring the adult tapeworm responsible for taeniosis [1]. The disease primarily affects impoverished rural communities in developing regions of Latin America, sub-Saharan Africa, and Asia, where free-range pig farming

and inadequate hygiene practices contribute to transmission [2].

Cysticercosis occurs when humans or pigs ingest *T. solium* eggs excreted in the feces of individuals with taeniosis [2]. Once ingested, the larvae migrate through the circulatory system and encyst in various organs, leading to cysticercosis [3]. In humans, the central nervous system (CNS) is a primary site of infection, resulting in neurocysticercosis (NCC), which is characterized by seizures, severe headaches, hydrocephalus, and other neurological impairments [3]. NCC is considered the most significant parasitic disease

affecting the nervous system and accounts for approximately 30% of acquired epilepsy cases in endemic regions [4].

T. solium cysticercosis is prevalent in both humans and pigs and remains an under-recognized public health concern [5]. The disease also causes significant economic losses due to the condemnation of infected pork [3]. Factors contributing to transmission include poor sanitation, indiscriminate fecal disposal, free-range pig farming, and the direct feeding of pigs with human waste. These conditions facilitate the exposure of pigs to *T. solium* eggs, perpetuating the disease cycle [6].

Several studies have reported the prevalence of porcine cysticercosis worldwide, particularly in Africa, Asia, India, and Latin America. In Nigeria, the prevalence of cysticercosis in pigs has been reported as high as 20.5% [7]. Globally, *T. solium* cysticercosis affects approximately 50 million people annually, causing an estimated 50,000 deaths, with neurocysticercosis being the most severe form. It is a major cause of epilepsy and neurological hospitalizations in endemic regions [8].

In Nigeria, *T. solium* cysticercosis remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in areas with widespread pig farming and pork consumption. Previous studies have reported varying prevalence rates across different states. In the Zuru area of Kebbi State, a study conducted over a decade ago found a porcine cysticercosis prevalence of 14.4% during post-mortem examinations [9]. However, there is a lack of recent data on the current status of the disease in this region. The absence of updated epidemiological information limits the development of effective control measures and public health policies, potentially allowing continued transmission between pigs and humans. Moreover, pigs from Zuru are frequently transported to other parts of Nigeria without adequate health monitoring, increasing the risk of disease spread.

Given these concerns, this study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by providing current data on the prevalence and risk factors associated with *T. solium* cysticercosis in Zuru, Kebbi State. The findings will support policymakers and stakeholders in formulating evidence-based control strategies, improving meat inspection protocols, and implementing targeted public health

interventions to mitigate the zoonotic and economic risks associated with the disease.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Zuru Local Government Area in Kebbi state, North-western Nigeria. Zuru is the headquarters of Zuru Emirate and is located on the following geographical coordinates: Latitude: 11° 26' 6.79" N Longitude: 5° 14' 5.78" E. The majority of the population lives in rural areas, and a significant number of urban dwellers engage in farming to supplement their other sources of income. Next to crop farming is animal rearing, which includes backyard pig rearing in some households [10].

Figure 1: Map of Kebbi state showing the study area [11]

2.2 Study Design

Cross-sectional study and convenience non-probability sampling techniques were used in the 8 sampling locations of the study areas (Amanawa/Barracks, Anguwar Zuru, Jankasa, Tudun Wada, Dabai, Ribah, Senchi, and Bedi). All the pigs presented for slaughter per day during the survey period were examined at ante-mortem and post-mortem, respectively [12].

A total of 184 blood samples were collected and analysed. Animals less than or equal to one year were grouped as young, and those above one year were recorded as old. The sex was determined by visual and physical examination of the external genital organs [13]. A Cysticercosis Ag ELISA

test kit (apDia, in vitro diagnostic kit. Belgium) was used to analyze the serum samples.

2.3 Sample Collection, Transport and Storage

Five milliliters (5 ml) of blood samples each were collected from pigs and transported in ice packs to the Central Research Laboratory, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, where the sera were kept at 20°C until analysis. The blood samples were centrifuged at 5,000 g for 5 minutes. The clotted cells settled at the bottom during centrifugation, leaving the serum at the top. The serum was harvested and stored in cryovials.

2.4 ELISA Test Principle and Procedure

The ELISA test was carried out according to the kit's manual. Pre-treated controls and serum samples were added to wells coated with B158C11A10 monoclonal antibodies specific to viable cysticerci antigens. During incubation, circulating antigens from viable cysticerci bind to the antibodies in the wells. Unbound serum proteins were removed through washing. To detect the antigen-antibody complex, specific peroxidase-conjugated B60H8A4 monoclonal antibodies were added. After washing the unbound conjugate, the wells were incubated with a chromogen solution containing tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) and

hydrogen peroxide, causing a blue color to develop in proportion to the bound immune complex. The reaction was stopped by adding 0.5M H₂SO₄, and the absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a spectrophotometer.

2.5 Data analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the results. A chi-square test was performed to assess the association between prevalence and some risk factors (sex and age) using SPSS version 20. In all analyses, a confidence level of 95% was adopted, and values of $P < 0.05$ were considered significant

3.0 Results

Out of the 184 sera samples examined for Porcine cysticercosis, 60 samples tested positive, giving a seroprevalence of 32.6% (Table 1). Table 2 shows the seroprevalence based on the respective areas where the samples were taken. The Sex-specific prevalence indicated that 36 of the 60 positive samples were from female pigs, while 24 were from males, as indicated in Table 3. Table 4 indicated that 42 of the 60 positive samples from the study were from old pigs, while 18 were from young pigs. A statistically significant association ($P=0.002$) was found between age and *T. solium* infection in the study.

Table 1: Overall Seroprevalence of *T. solium* Cysticercosis in Pigs in Zuru

Sex	Number of samples	Number positive	Prevalence(%)
Male	66	24	13.0
Female	118	36	19.6
Total	184	60	32.6

Table 2: Seroprevalence of *T. solium* Cysticercosis in Pigs in each location in Zuru LGA

Location	No. of samples	Ag Elisa +ve	χ^2	P value		
Amanawa/Barrack	30	11	3.807	0.802		
Anguwar zuru	31	14				
Jankasa	20	6				
Tudun Wada	24	7				
Dabai	18	4				
Ribah	23	7				
Senchi	21	6				
Bedi	17	5				
Total	184	60(32.6%)				

Table 3: Sex Specific seroprevalence of Cysticercosis in Pigs in Zuru

	Male	Female	Total	<i>p</i> -value	χ^2	OR
Positive	24(36.4%)	36(30.5%)	60(32.6%)	0.416	0.660	0.8
Negative	42	82	124			Ref
Total	66	118	184			

Table 4: Age Specific seroprevalence of Cysticercosis in Pigs in Zuru

	Young	Old	Total	<i>p</i> Value	χ^2	OR
Positive	18(21.2%)	42(42.4%)	60(32.6)	0.002	9.396	2.7
Negative	67	57	124			
Total	85	99	184			

4.0 Discussion

This study reported an overall seroprevalence of porcine cysticercosis at 32.6%. This prevalence is notably higher than the 14.4% reported in Zuru, Nigeria [9] and the 7.6% reported in Plateau State, Nigeria [14]. Similarly, it exceeds the prevalence of 18% obtained by Garcia-Noval et al. [15]. However, the result closely aligns with the 27.7% prevalence found in northern Cameroon [16]. The relatively high prevalence observed in this study could be attributed to the total number of animals sampled during the study period. Additionally, the pigs examined did not receive any form of medication, which may have increased their susceptibility to infection.

Despite the observed high prevalence, the result of this study is lower than the 52.3% reported in the Northern Senatorial Zone of Taraba State [17], the 40.8% prevalence in Burundi [18], and the 45.3% prevalence in Tanzania's Mbozi district [19]. One possible explanation for the lower prevalence in this study is the sensitivity of the diagnostic method employed, which detects only the presence of living cysticerci and cannot identify deteriorated or calcified cysticerci. This limitation contrasts with antibody detection assays, which can identify past infections regardless of the parasite's viability [20]. The reliance on circulating antigen levels, which correlate with the quantity and size of lesions, may have contributed to the lower prevalence result in this study compared to the aforementioned regions.

The variation in prevalence across different study locations highlights the influence of environmental and husbandry factors. The highest seroprevalence was recorded in Ungwan Zuru (45.1%) and Amanawa (36.6%), whereas Dabai had the lowest prevalence at 22.2%. Notably, Amanawa/Barracks,

Sanchi, and Anguwan Zuru had larger pig populations than other locations, which, coupled with factors such as poor sanitation and inadequate pig husbandry practices, could explain the higher prevalence in these areas. Moreover, Anguwan Zuru and Amanawa/Barracks had more slum areas, characterized by poor hygiene, which may have exacerbated the Cysticercosis-taeniosis complex. These findings suggest that environmental conditions and management practices significantly influence disease transmission.

Regarding sex distribution, the prevalence of cysticercosis was slightly higher in females than in males. This observation could be due to the larger proportion of females in the sampled population (Table 2). However, the difference in seroprevalence between sexes was not statistically significant, indicating that both males and females are equally susceptible to infection. These findings are consistent with results from the Chaco region in Bolivia, where no significant sex-based differences in prevalence were reported [21]. Contrarily, studies conducted in Guatemala [6], Tanzania [19], and Plateau State, Nigeria [14] have documented a significantly higher prevalence in females than in males. The discrepancies between studies may stem from variations in sample size, management practices, and epidemiological factors in different regions.

Furthermore, a statistically significant association was found between cysticercosis prevalence and age ($P=0.002$). The significant difference in cysticercosis prevalence observed across age groups can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, older pigs have had a longer duration of exposure to contaminated environments, including water, feed, and soil containing *T. solium* eggs, increasing their likelihood of infection. Additionally, the cumulative

risk of ingestion plays a role, as older pigs are more likely to have repeatedly consumed contaminated feed or water sources over time. This result aligns with the general understanding that older pigs have a higher risk of infection due to prolonged environmental exposure, reinforcing the need for targeted control measures to reduce transmission in endemic areas.

5.0 Conclusion

This study found a 32.6% seroprevalence of porcine cysticercosis, with the highest rates in Ungwan Zuru (45.1%) and Amanawa (36.6%), likely due to poor sanitation and high pig density. The study found no statistically significant difference in prevalence between sexes, suggesting that both male and female pigs are equally susceptible to infection. However, a significant association between age and prevalence was observed, with older pigs being at higher risk, likely due to prolonged exposure to infection sources.

6.0 Recommendations

To address the public health risks associated with *T. solium* infections, there is a need for public awareness and campaigns on the dangers of consuming undercooked infected pork. More extensive studies, especially during festive periods when pig slaughter rates are high, are recommended to assess the disease's prevalence better. Further research into human taeniosis and cysticercosis during these high-slaughter periods is also advised to better understand the disease's impact on human health in the region.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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